

DIAGNOSIS AND TREATMENT OF UROGENITAL FORM OF DIABETIC AUTONOMIC NEUROPATHY IN PATIENTS WITH TYPE 2 DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract. *Diabetes mellitus (DM) is common in all countries of the world. According to the World Health Organization, there are currently about 422 million people with diabetes on the planet, and their number is growing progressively. It is well known that DM is dangerous primarily for its long-term complications, such as nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy, cardiovascular diseases and others. Diabetic neuropathy, alone, is often found in both types of DM. The frequency of its development increases with age and duration of DM. The urogenital form of diabetic autonomic neuropathy (DAN) is one of the forms of autonomic neuropathy, the main manifestation of which is erectile dysfunction (ED). The purpose of our study was to study the features and severity of clinical manifestations of ED depending on compensation and duration of the disease.*

Keywords: *diabetes mellitus, diabetic autonomic neuropathy, erectile dysfunction, treatment.*

Introduction: Diabetes mellitus (DM) is common in all countries of the world. According to the World Health Organization, there are currently about 422 million people with diabetes on the planet, and their number is growing rapidly [1,2]. It is well known that DM is dangerous primarily because of its long-term complications, such as nephropathy, retinopathy, neuropathy, cardiovascular diseases, and others.

Diabetic neuropathy, alone, is often found in both types of DM. Its frequency of development increases with age and duration of DM.

The urogenital form of diabetic autonomic neuropathy (DAN) is one of the forms of autonomic (vegetative) neuropathy, the main manifestation of which is erectile dysfunction (ED) [5].

ED occurs in 50-60% of men suffering from DM. [6,7] The risk of developing ED in diabetes mellitus is 3 times higher than in the healthy population [7,8]. ED can be the first symptom of diabetes mellitus. Still, in more than 50% of patients with diabetes, it occurs within the first 10 years of the disease and is often the first manifestation of neuropathy or macroangiopathy [8]. Recently, more and more studies have appeared showing that ED can be an early indirect sign of the onset and progression of atherosclerosis in diabetes mellitus [9], which demonstrates the importance of early diagnosis of ED for identifying risk groups and improving preventive measures to prevent the development of late complications, such as diabetic foot syndrome and severe macroangiopathy. In addition, several studies have revealed a relationship between the development of ED and the degree of long-term compensation of diabetes mellitus (glycated hemoglobin levels), the presence of late complications, concomitant diseases, and the therapy being carried out. In patients with diabetes and concomitant arterial hypertension, ED occurs in more than 80% of cases [10,11]. Since the etiology of ED in diabetes mellitus is multifactorial

(hypogonadism, neuropathy, vascular disorders, decompensation of diabetes, psychogenic factors, the influence of drugs used to treat complications of diabetes), accurate diagnosis of the form of ED and the degree of contribution of each of these factors will improve the qualitative effect of the therapy and, as a result, improve the quality of life of patients with diabetes.

Along with this, due to insufficient coverage in the literature of clinical manifestations of ED in patients with diabetes, special attention should be paid to analyzing the characteristics and severity of clinical symptoms of disorders depending on the type and duration. Since, according to many researchers, the leading pathogenetic factor of ED in patients with diabetes mellitus is neuropathy, and the number of visits for ED is higher than for other early manifestations of nervous system damage, timely motivation of patients for more thorough compensation of diabetes and compliance with the doctor's recommendations will prevent the occurrence and development of more formidable complications of diabetes mellitus, such as cardiac and gastrointestinal forms of neuropathy, diabetic foot syndrome. Active detection and study of the nature of ED in patients with diabetes will allow not only to reasonably choose methods of treatment for patients with diabetes, which will contribute to improving the quality of their life but also to more rationally prevent the development of other neurogenic and vasculogenic complications of the underlying disease. No less important is the development of a system of medical care for men with sexual dysfunction, similar to the systems that actively assist patients with complications such as nephropathy, retinopathy, coronary heart disease, and diabetic foot syndrome.

Our study aimed to investigate the characteristics and severity of clinical manifestations of ED depending on the compensation and duration of the disease.

Materials and methods. The study involved 30 men with type 2 diabetes. The control group consisted of 7 practically healthy people. The exclusion criteria were the absence of benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH) in patients. All patients underwent conventional general clinical and biochemical studies. The state of diabetes compensation was assessed by the content of glycated hemoglobin (HbA1C). The level of glycemia was determined by the glucose oxidase method on an empty stomach and 2 hours after breakfast. The severity of erectile dysfunction was determined by questionnaires using the International Index of Erectile Function - 5 (IIEF-5). EF was determined using the IIEF-5 questionnaire, which allows for assessing five components of sexual function (erection, orgasm, sexual desire, satisfaction from sexual intercourse, and general sexual satisfaction). The questionnaire consists of five questions, each offering five answer options. Based on the answers to the questions, the total number of points is summed up, which allows us to determine the norm (21–25 points) and different degrees of erectile dysfunction (16–20 points – mild, 11–15 points – moderately mild, 5–10 points – severe).

Appendix 1. International Index of Erectile Dysfunction (IIEF)

	Almost never or never	Rarely (less than half the time)	Sometimes (about half the time)	Often (more than half of the cases)	Almost always or always
1. How often have you had an erection during sexual activity recently?	1	2	3	4	5

2. How often recently have you had an erection that was sufficient for insertion of the penis (for the beginning of sexual intercourse)	1	2	3	4	5
3. When attempting sexual intercourse, how often were you able to insert the penis (start sexual intercourse)?	1	2	3	4	5
4. How often have you recently been able to maintain an erection after the start of sexual intercourse?	1	2	3	4	5
5. How difficult was it to maintain an erection during and until the end of intercourse?	1 extremely difficult	2 very difficult	3 difficult	4 not very difficult	5 not difficult

Results: HbA1c content in patients with type 2 diabetes exceeded the control values by 55.5% relative to the control. Similar changes were observed in fasting and 2-hour postprandial glycemia values, which increased by 54.5 and 55%, respectively, indicating diabetes decompensation. Among the examined patients with type 2 diabetes, the presence of ED was detected in 100% of patients as a result of questioning using the IIEF-5 questionnaires. Among them, ED was not detected in 6 patients. At the same time, mild erectile dysfunction was detected in 30% (10 patients) – 17.4 ± 2.3 points, moderate ED in 54% (18 patients) – 12.2 ± 1.3 points. Severe ED was detected in 2 patients, with an average score of 8.4 ± 1.13 points (this constituted 6% of the total number of those examined with sexual dysfunction). (Table 1)

Table 1. Carbohydrate metabolism parameters in patients with type 2 diabetes upon admission ($M \pm m$)

Tests	Control, n=7	Upon admission, n=30
HbA1c %	$4,5 \pm 1,02$	$10,13 \pm 0,8^*$
Fasting glycemia, mmol/l	$4,6 \pm 0,8$	$10,1 \pm 0,35^*$
Postprandial glycemia, mmol/l	$5,9 \pm 0,3$	$13,1 \pm 0,6^*$

Note: n – number of patients examined * – presence of reliability ($P < 0.05$) compared to control

In patients with a severe form of the disease, a more reliable decrease in erectile function was found to 7.5 ± 1.13 points (by 73%), while in patients with moderate severity, this indicator was reduced by 54%. (Table 2)

The study of EF depending on the duration of the disease showed that the longer the duration of diabetes is, the more pronounced the ED is. Thus, in the group of patients with a

duration of diabetes of up to 5 years, a reliable decrease in EF by 34% is noted, and with a duration of the disease from 5 to 10 years – by 56%. In the group of more than 10 years, this indicator was significantly lower in relation to the control and amounted to 6.8 ± 0.3 points. (Table 3)

Table 2. ED indicators in patients with type 2 diabetes depending on the severity of the disease

Indicator	control n-7	moderate severity form n-21	severe form n-9
IIEF-5, in points	24±2,24	11,2±2,3 *	7,5±1,13*

Table 3. ED indicators in patients with type 2 diabetes depending on the duration of the disease

Indicator	Control n-7	Duration of DM, years		
		0-5 years n-8	5-10 years n-18	More than 10 years n-4
IIEF-5, in points	24±2,24	18,4±2,3*	11,5±1,1*	6,8±0,3

Conclusion: Erectile dysfunction occurs in men with type 2 diabetes mellitus aged 55-59 years. According to the IIEF-5 questionnaire, 54% of patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus are diagnosed with moderate erectile dysfunction. The severity of erectile dysfunction is associated with the severity and duration of diabetes.

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